

Synthesis of some New Pyrimidine and Condensed Pyrimidine Derivatives

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Many derivatives of condensed pyrimidine find biological applications¹. Cinnamionitriles are versatile reagent for the synthesis of enamionitrile, pyrimidines. Thus, the reaction of the β -naphthylidene malononitrile (**1**) with urea in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 afforded the oxypyrimidine (**2a**). The thioxopyrimidine (**2b**) was also obtained from reaction of **1** with thiourea under the same condition. Enaminonitriles are used in heterocyclic system. Thus condensation of **2b** with cyclohexanone in presence of anhydrous $ZnCl_2$ afforded the quinolinopyrimidine (**3**)². **2b** on reaction with formamide in presence of formic acid gave the pyrimidopyrimidine (**4**). Hydrazinolysis of **2b** using excess of hydrazine hydrate yielded the pyrazolopyrimidine (**5**) with the evolution of H_2S gas. Condensation of the enaminonitrile (**2b**) with benzoyl isothiocyanate in dioxane afforded the pyrimidopyrimidine (**7**) presumably via the thiourea derivatives (**6**)³. Reaction of **2b** with carbon disulphide in DMF yielded pyrimido-pyrimidine (**8**)⁴. The synthesis of cyclohexanopyrimidinone (**9**) was achieved by reacting **2a** with formic acid (Scheme 1).

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer and 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian HA 100 spectrometer (100 MHz). Microanalysis was carried out at the Microanalytical Unit, Faculty of Science, Cairo University.

4-Amino-6-naphthyl-(1H)-pyrimidine-5-carbonitriles (2a, 2b): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol), urea or thiourea (0.01 mol), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (0.03 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid obtained was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. **2a**, m.p. 250° (Found: C, 68.60; H, 3.70; N, 21.30. $C_{15}H_{10}ON_4$ requires: C, 68.69; H, 3.84; N, 21.36%); **2b**, 278° (Found: C, 64.70; H, 3.50; N, 20.10; S, 11.50. $C_{15}H_{10}N_4S$ requires: C, 64.73; H, 3.62; N, 20.13, S, 11.52%), ν_{max} 3 388 (NH_2), 2 214 cm^{-1} (CN), δ 8.7(1H, s, NH), 6.0 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.8–7.6 (7H, m, ArH).

4-Naphthyl-9-amino-2-thioxo-(1H)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydroquinolino[2,3-d]pyrimidine (3): To a solution of **2b** (0.01 mol) in cyclohexanone (15 ml), anhydrous $ZnCl_2$ (0.01 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 min. The complex with zinc chloride was separated from the solution, the mixture dissolved in 40% NaOH (20 ml) and extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated and the resulting solid was

Scheme 1

crystallised from benzene: m.p. $> 300^\circ$ (Found: C, 70.30; H, 5.10; N, 15.60; S, 8.90. $C_{21}H_{18}N_4S$ requires: C, 70.36; H, 5.06; N, 15.63; S, 8.95%), ν_{max} 3 400 (NH_2), 1 580 cm^{-1} (C=N), δ 7.8–7.6 (7H, m, ArH), 2.2 (2H, br s, 2H-9), 1.9 (2H, brs, 2H-6), 1.5 (4H, br s, 2H-7, 2H-8), 6.0 (2H, s, NH_2), 8.3 (1H, br s, NH).

4-Naphthyl-5-amino-2-thioxo-(1H)-pyrimido[4,5-d]pyrimidine (4): A mixture of **2b** (0.01 mol), formamide (15 ml) and formic acid (3 drops) was refluxed for 6 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture, to which water had been added, the solid obtained was crystallised from n-butanol as pale yellow crystals: m.p. 300° (Found: C, 62.90; H, 3.60; N, 22.90; S, 10.50. $C_{16}H_{11}N_5S$ requires: C, 62.93; H, 3.63; N, 22.94; S, 10.50%), ν_{max} 3 400 (NH_2), 1 560 cm^{-1} (C=N), δ 6.3 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.8–7.6 (8H, m, ArH pyrimidine protons).

NOTE

4-Naphthyl-5-amino-2-thioxo-(1H)-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine (5) : A mixture of **2b** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.03 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol : m.p. 230° (Found : C, 61.40; H, 3.70; N, 23.80; S, 10.90. C₁₅H₁₁N₅S requires : C, 61.41; H, 3.78; N, 23.88; S, 10.93%), ν_{\max} 3 450 (NH₂), 3 310 cm⁻¹ (NH), δ 8.1 (1H, br s, NH), 4.3 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.6–7.2 (7H, m, ArH).

4-Naphthyl-5-amino-6-benzoyl-2,7-dithioxo-1,8-dihydropyrimido[4,5-d]pyrimidine (7) : A mixture of benzoyl isothiocyanate (prepared by refluxing a mixture of 0.012 mol ammonium thiocyanate and 0.01 mol benzoyl chloride in 20 ml dioxane for 20 min) and **2b** (0.01 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then poured in water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals : m.p. > 300° (Found : C, 62.50; H, 3.40; N, 15.80; S, 14.50. C₂₃H₁₅ON₅S₂ requires : C, 62.56; H, 3.42; N, 15.86; S, 14.52%), ν_{\max} 3 410 (NH₂), 1 670 cm⁻¹ (CO), δ 6.3 (2H, s, NH₂), 8.2 (1H, br s, NH), 7.8–7.2 (12H, m, ArH).

4-Naphthyl-2,5,7-trithioxo-1,6,8-trihydropyrimido[4,5-d]pyrimidine (8) : A mixture of **2b** (0.01 mol) in dimethyl formamide (30 ml) and carbon disulphide (20 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 10 h. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the solid residue was triturated with water to give the product which was

crystallised from methanol : m.p. 300° (Found : C, 54.10; H, 2.80; N, 15.80; S, 27.10. C₁₆H₁₀N₄S₃ requires : C, 54.21; H, 2.84; N, 15.81; S, 27.14%), ν_{\max} 3 200 (NH), 2 250 (SH), 1 340 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

4-Naphthyl-5-oxo-2-thioxo-1,6-dihydropyrimido[4,5-d]pyrimidine (9) : A solution of **2b** (0.01 mol) in formic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 7 h. The excess formic acid was then removed under reduced pressure and the solid residue was crystallised from n-butanol : m.p. > 300° (Found : C, 62.90; H, 2.90; N, 18.30; S, 10.40. C₁₆H₉ON₄S requires : C, 62.94; H, 2.97; N, 18.35; S, 10.50%), ν_{\max} 3 280 (NH), 1 650 (CO), 1 540 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

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